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Review Paper

Clinical Review of Antidiabetic Drugs: Implications for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Management

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ABSTRACT

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Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a worldwide pandemic, as can be seen from the world cartographic map of diabetes by the International Diabetes Federation. Diabetes mellitus is a chronic, progressive, partially unravelled metabolic disease predominantly defined by hyperglycaemia. Impaired secretion of insulin, tissue resistance to the action of insulin, or both are the most prevalent underlying causes of the pathophysiology of T2DM, a disease spectrum that was initially due to tissue insulin resistance and eventually evolving towards a condition with total loss of secretory function of the beta cells of the pancreas. T2DM is a principal cause of the extremely high increase in the incidence of non-communicable diseases in both developed and developing countries. We attempt to define in this mini review the present management concepts, from the range of medicines prescribed now for the drug management, to reduce raised blood glucose in T2DM. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a growing, worldwide health burden closely associated with the obesity epidemic. Patients with T2DM are at particularly high risk for both microvascular (such as retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy) and microvascular complications (such as cardiovascular comorbidities) due to hyperglycaemia and individual constituents of the insulin resistance (metabolic) syndrome. Environmental conditions (e.g., obesity, poor diet and physical inactivity) and genetics are responsible for the various pathophysiological disruptions that underlie compromised glucose homeostasis in T2DM.

The pathogenic role of inflammation in type 1 and type 2 diabetes is discussed, as well as the mediators and anti-inflammatory therapies. In addition, the role of different organs in diabetes mellitus is emphasized, including the adipose tissue and obesity, gut microbiota, and pancreatic-cells. The expression of pancreatic Langerhans -cell islet inflammation, oxidative stress, and defective insulin production and secretion are discussed.

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INTRODUCTION

Definition of diabetes mellitus (DM) - Chronic hyperglycaemia is a metabolic disorder resulting from either an inadequate secretion of insulin, or an impairment of insulin action, or both. Interestingly, insulin acts significantly as an anabolic hormone with effects on the metabolism of carbohydrates, lipids, and proteins [1]. The metabolic defects of diabetes primarily act on tissues including adipose tissue, skeletal muscles, and the liver through insulin resistance. The intensity of the symptoms can differ based on the time and extent of diabetes. Patients with high blood sugar levels, especially those with a total absence of insulin, like children, might develop symptoms like excessive hunger, polydipsia, dysuria, weight loss, hunger, and visual disturbances. Individuals with diabetes can become symptom-free, particularly type 2 diabetic patients in the initial stages [2].

If left untreated, uncontrolled diabetes can result in several complications like coma, confusion, and in extreme cases, death due to ketoacidosis or nonketotic hyperosmolar syndrome not treated. In

2019, diabetes caused 1.5 million deaths, 48% of which were before the age of 70. Diabetes also caused an additional 460,000 deaths from kidney disease, and approximately 20% of cardiovascular-related deaths from high blood glucose levels. During the period of 2000-2019, there was a 3% increase in standardized mortality rates due to diabetes. In lower-middle-income countries, the mortality rate due to diabetes increased by 13%. Conversely, the chance of dying from any one of the four main non-communicable diseases (cardiovascular diseases, cancer, chronic respiratory diseases, or diabetes) between the ages of 30 and 70 went down by 22% globally between 2000 and 2019.

How much glucose is in the blood?

Having in mind that T2DM entails a rise in blood glucose, it is worthwhile to know how much glucose is present in the blood stream initially, and then the variables that affect the blood glucose both exogenous and endogenous variables. The quantity of glucose in the blood is tightly regulated about 5-10 grams in the blood at any time, depending on the person's size.

Blood Glucose Chart			
Mg/DL	Fasting	After Eating	2-3 Hours After Eating
Normal	80-100	170-200	120-140
Impaired Glucose	101-125	190-230	140-160
Diabetic	126+	220-300	200+

Classification of Diabetes Mellitus -

Classification:

Diabetes can be divided into the

following broad categories:

1. Type 1 diabetes (as a result of autoimmune) - cell destruction, typically

resulting in absolute insulin deficiency, including latent autoimmune diabetes of adulthood

2. Type 2 diabetes (as a consequence of a progressive impairment of sufficient) - cell insulin secretion often in the setting of insulin resistance

Certain forms of diabetes secondary to other aetiologies, i.e., monogenic diabetes syndromes (e.g., neonatal diabetes and maturity-onset diabetes of the young), exocrine pancreatic diseases (e.g., cystic fibrosis and pancreatitis), and drug- or chemical-induced diabetes (e.g., with glucocorticoid therapy, in HIV/AIDS

1. Increased thirst.
2. Increased urination.
3. Increased hunger.
4. Weight loss.
5. Fatigue.
6. Blurred vision.
7. Slow healing of cuts and wounds.
8. Increased frequency of infections.
9. Numbness or tingling in hands and feet.
10. Darkened areas of skin, usually in the armpits and neck.

Major endogenous factors that lower the blood glucose -

The major endogenous mechanism to lower the blood glucose is to deliver glucose into the cells (all cells can use glucose). If the blood glucose exceeds about 180 milligrams/deciliter, then loss of glucose into the urine can occur. The blood glucose is reduced by cellular uptake using glut transporters. Some cells have transporters that are responsive to the presence of insulin to activate, others have transporters that do not need insulin for activation. Insulin responsive glucose transporters in muscle cells and adipose cells result in a decrease in glucose levels

treatment, or following organ transplantation)

Gestational diabetes mellitus (diabetes detected in the second or third trimester of pregnancy that was not obviously overt diabetes before gestation)

Symptoms -

Type 2 diabetes symptoms can creep up on a person. Many times, individuals can live for years with type 2 diabetes and be unaware of it. If symptoms are present, they might include:

particularly after carbohydrate-containing meals. Exercise has the ability to increase the glucose use in muscle, which in turn increases glucose cellular uptake and decrease the blood glucose levels. During exercise, when the metabolic demands of skeletal muscle can rise more than 100 fold, and during the absorptive period (after a meal), the insulin-responsive glut4 transporters permit the swift uptake of glucose into fat and muscle tissue, thus avoiding large swings in blood sugar levels.

MAJOR EXOGENOUS FACTORS THAT:

1. Decrease the blood glucose –

A decrease in dietary carbohydrate intake can lower the blood glucose. An increase in activity or exercise usually decreases the blood glucose (11). Numerous different medications, using numerous different mechanisms, exist to decrease the blood glucose. Medications will delay sucrose and starch absorption (alpha-glucosidase inhibitors), retard gastric emptying (GLP-1 agonists, DPP-4 inhibitors), amplify insulin secretion (sulfonylureas, meglitinides, GLP-1 agonists, DPP-4 inhibitors), decrease gluconeogenesis (biguanides), decrease insulin resistance (biguanides, thiazolidinedione's), and enhance urinary glucose loss (SGLT-2 inhibitors). Medication use will also possess potential side effects.

2. Possible dual role of an insulin-dependent glucose transporter (glut4)

A common metaphor is to think of the insulin/glut transporter system as a key/lock mechanism. Common wisdom states that the purpose of insulin-responsive glut4 transporters is to facilitate glucose uptake when blood insulin levels are elevated. But, a lock serves two purposes: to let someone in and/or to keep someone out. So, one of the consequences of the insulin-responsive glut4 transporter is to exclude glucose from the muscle and adipose cells, too, during low levels of insulin. The cells that need glucose ("glucose-dependent") don't need insulin to allow glucose entry into the cell (non-insulin-responsive transporters). Teleological, it would "make no sense" for cells that need glucose to contain insulin responsive glut4 transporters. Cells that need glucose contain glut1, glut2, glut3, glut5 transporters - none of which are insulin-responsive it doesn't make sense to have a

lock on a door that you want people to pass through). Under basal (low insulin) conditions, the majority of glucose is utilized by the brain and carried by non-insulin-responsive glut1 and glut. So maybe one of the roles of the insulin-responsive glucose uptake in muscle and adipose is to prevent glucose FROM entering these cells at basal (low insulin) conditions, in order to leave the glucose supply available for the glucose-dependent tissue (renal medulla, blood cells).

3. Therapeutic strategies in non-insulin management of type 2 diabetes mellitus -

Several non-insulin oral therapies have been developed for the management of type 2 DM. They are classified under the following sub-headings:

1. Insulin Secretagogues
2. Biguanides
3. Insulin Sensitizers
4. Alpha Glucosidase Inhibitors
5. Amylin antagonists
6. SGLT2 inhibitors

1. Insulin Secretagogues:

These group of medications (particularly sulfonylureas and metiglinides) work by enhancing the release of insulin from pancreas through binding to sulfonylurea receptor (SUR) of ATP sensitive potassium channel on pancreatic cells. 1st generation sulfonylurea is Tolbutamide, Chlorpropamide, Tolazamide, Acetohexamide and 2nd generation sulfonylurea includes Glibenclamide, Glipizide, Glimepiride.

2nd generation sulfonylurea was developed because of higher potency, faster onset of action, shorter half-lives and longer duration of action. Typical side effects of sulfonylurea are evidence of low blood sugar level like dizziness, sweating, confusion and nervousness. It may also be hunger, weight gain, skin reaction, stomach upset and dark coloured urine.

natural insulin, lowers intake of glucose by the intestine and lowers liver production of glucose. Biguanides lower hepatic glucose production through inhibition of gluconeogenesis and enhancement of glycolysis. They enhance insulin signalling through augmenting insulin receptor activity. In contrast to insulin secretagogues, these compounds do not affect insulin secretion directly. Various molecules in this class are

Metformin, Phenformin and Buformin. Phenformin

Metiglinide is the prototype molecule which is benzoic acid derivative of non-sulfonylurea moiety of Glibenclamide. These drugs have their action by closing the ATP sensitive potassium channel present on plasma membrane of pancreatic β cells. Repaginate and Nateglinide are other molecules utilized in this class.

2. Biguanides:

It acts by enhancing body's response to

and Buformin were removed from clinical practice due to a high rate of linked lactic acidosis whereas Metformin has a significantly reduced risk of lactic acidosis, therefore used extensively. Biguanides are not hypoglycaemic or weight-gaining, possess anti-hypertriglyceridemia effect and vasoprotective effects. Biguanides inhibit fatty acid breakdown by activation of

AMP-dependent protein kinase. But biguanides shares a common adverse effect of gastrointestinal distress, such as diarrhoea, cramps, nausea, vomiting, and enhanced flatulence. Its Long-term administration is related with reduced absorption of vitamin B12.

3. Insulin Sensitizers:

The insulin sensitizers are also referred to as Peroxisome Proliferator Activated Receptor agonists (PPARs). PPARs are the controllers of protein and carbohydrate metabolism and they help in the glucose homeostasis. These are nuclear hormone receptor superfamily of ligand activated transcription factors. These receptors are of three sub-types i.e. PPAR α and β . PPAR α is glucose homeostasis specific. The agonists of PPAR α are usually thiazolidinedione and are referred to as "glitazones". Glitazones make the cells insulin-sensitive. They also reduce the systemic fatty acid production and their uptake. Activation of PPAR α enhances the glucose uptake by skeletal muscles and reduces the glucose production by slowing the gluconeogenesis. The first-generation molecules of this class are Pioglitazone, Rosiglitazone and Ciglitazone. They are linked to shared side effects such as oedema, weight gain, macular oedema and heart failure. They could induce hypoglycaemia when used together with other anti-diabetic medicines as well as they reduce haematocrit, reduce haemoglobin content and rise bone fracture threat.

First line medications for the treatment of DM were replaced by second line drugs as a result of the common side effects of the former group of drugs.

CONCLUSION -

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a top cause of

renal failure, ASCVD, non-traumatic amputation of the lower limbs, blindness, and mortality globally. It is a severe, long-term medical disorder that needs to be addressed using a multidisciplinary team, including healthcare workers, dietitians, patient educators, patients, and families. Lifestyle modification aimed at controlling body weight and obesity treatment, coupled with patient education, is necessary for all diabetic patients. Treatment plans can be tailored and medication(s) selected according to a patient's risk factors, HbA1C at present, efficacy of medication, ease of medication use, patient's finances/insurance/costs, and risk of side effects like hypoglycaemia and weight gain. Therapeutic effectiveness should be assessed as often as possible through diagnostic blood testing (HbA1C) as well as diabetic complication monitoring (e.g., retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy). In addition, forceful actions of doctors and encouraging compliance of patients are the two significant factors in the prevention and control of diabetes. Sociocultural factors should be properly considered. For instance, in the case of religious fasting (for instance, in the holy month of Ramadan), the application of pharmacologic agents that cause hypoglycaemia should be applied cautiously and insulin doses (for instance, premix type) should be titrated suitably and the patient should be instructed for monitoring of blood glucose and breaking the fast as necessary.

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